

Goldbach light

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The Goldbach Conjecture (GC) states that every even integer $n > 6$ is a sum of two odd primes.

Now, the set of positive even integers for $n > 6$ is the union of two disjoint sets:

$$E1 \equiv \{\text{twice odds}\} = \{2(2m + 1), m = 2, 3, 4, \dots\} = \{10, 14, 18, \dots\}$$

$$E2 \equiv \{\text{twice evens}\} = \{2(2m), m = 2, 3, 4, \dots\} = \{8, 12, 16, \dots\}$$

We know the set of odd primes can be decomposed into disjoint sets according to gap width **[1]**; let's start with twins:

$$P2 \equiv \{\text{primes } p: p + 2 \text{ is also prime}\}$$

Choose arbitrary $n = 2k, k > 3$. Then

$$2k = p + p + 2 = 2(p + 1) \Rightarrow k = p + 1 \Rightarrow k \text{ is even} \Rightarrow k = 2m \Rightarrow n = 4m$$

So the set of twins P2 sum-covers E2.

Next, let

$$P4 \equiv \{\text{primes } p: p + 4 \text{ is also prime}\}$$

$$2k = p + p + 4 = 2(p + 2) \Rightarrow k = p + 2 \Rightarrow k \text{ is odd} \Rightarrow k = 2m + 1 \Rightarrow n = 2(2m + 1)$$

So the set P4 sum-covers E1.

To continue, let

$$P6 \equiv \{\text{primes } p: p + 6 \text{ is also prime}\}$$

$$2k = p + p + 6 = 2(p + 3) \Rightarrow k = p + 3 \Rightarrow k \text{ is even} \Rightarrow k = 2m \Rightarrow n = 4m$$

So the set P6 also sum-covers E2.

Let now

$$P8 \equiv \{\text{primes } p: p + 8 \text{ is also prime}\}$$

$$2k = p + p + 8 = 2(p + 4) \Rightarrow k = p + 4 \Rightarrow k \text{ is odd} \Rightarrow k = 2m + 1 \Rightarrow n = 2(2m + 1)$$

So the set P8 also sum-covers E1.

Clearly then

$P2 \cup P6 \cup P10 \cup \dots$ will sum-cover E2

and

$P_4 \cup P_8 \cup P_{12} \cup \dots$ will sum-cover E_1 .

Thus when an even integer $n > 6$ is divided by 2 and yields an odd integer, it will belong to set E_1 and some twosome from

$P_4 \cup P_8 \cup P_{12} \cup \dots$

is guaranteed to provide summability. Otherwise the set E_2 enters, and some twosomes from the set

$P_2 \cup P_6 \cup P_{10} \cup \dots$

are sure to offer sum-cover.

Some samples now:

$8/2 = 4 \Rightarrow 8 \in E_2 \Rightarrow P_2$ will cover: (3 + 5)

$10/2 = 5 \Rightarrow 10 \in E_1 \Rightarrow P_4$ will cover: (3 + 7)

$128/2 = 64 \Rightarrow 128 \in E_2 \Rightarrow P_6$ will cover: (61 + 67)

$126/2 = 63 \Rightarrow 126 \in E_1 \Rightarrow P_8$ will cover: (59 + 67)

$1384/2 = 692 \Rightarrow 1348 \in E_2 \Rightarrow P_{18}$ will cover: (683 + 701)

$\Rightarrow P_{38}$ will also cover: (673 + 711)

Thus GC is likely over-determined by the primes!

Of course, no recipe is provided here for actually finding the appropriate prime pairings as summands; after all, primes are not really predictable in the ordinary sense. And uniqueness should not be expected; indeed, simply doubling primes $p > 3$, i.e.

10, 14, 22, 26, 34, 38, ...

yields many (though obviously not all) evens above 6, some also covered by the gap counters.

However, a plausible existence argument has been offered.

[1] A. Cusmariu, 'Prime gapology', zenodo.org/zenodo.13150614, Aug. 2024.